

Cobalt(III) Complexes of Oximes and related Schiff Bases as Models for Vitamin B₁₂*

KAILASH C. DASH

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004

Dioximes and oxime based Schiff bases form cobalt(III) complexes in presence of imidazole base which are believed to be true non-alkyl analogues of cobaloximes. The bis-bidentate or the tetradentate ligands used provide four nitrogen donors in the equatorial position and exhibit nearly all of the same coordination chemistry as vitamin B₁₂ itself and are believed to be model compounds for vitamin B₁₂. A wide range of ligands are shown to occupy the axial positions, probably largely due to the less stringent steric requirements of the inorganic species. The dioximes and the related series of conjugated and unconjugated tetradentate ligands formed several cobalt(III) complexes of the type [Co(DH₂)(B)(X)] (DH₂ = dimethylglyoxime, B = imidazole base, X = anion), [Co(HL)₂X₂] (HL = H₂Me₂en, H₂Me₂pn, H₂Me(Ph)en, H₂Me₂o-phen) as well as [Co(L)(B)(X)] and [Co(L)(B)₂(X)]. The electrochemical data establish the presence of cobalt(III) centre. The complexes are characterised by electronic, infrared, mass, ESCA and nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectra as well as thermogravimetric data.

It is indeed a pleasure and proud privilege on my part to have been chosen through a peer review for the Professor Priyadarajan Ray Memorial Award and Lecture 1990, of the Indian Chemical Society. Professor Priyadarajan Ray was acclaimed world-wide as a distinguished chemist, second to none, for his outstanding and pioneering research on various aspects of coordination chemistry and its applications. The present lecture will outline our humble contribution in one aspect of coordination chemistry.

Since Alfred Werner's¹ discovery of coordination compounds of transition metals in the late nineteenth century, the developments in this area of research has been expanding at an exponential rate in many directions making this a truly interdisciplinary topic with diverse applications in various fields. Many new types of compounds have been synthesised emphasising the underlying theoretical concepts, new experimental techniques and ever newer applications, all of which pose a challenge to any practising inorganic chemist. Indeed, one can compare a synthetic coordination

chemist to a geographical explorer of the past, moving in several directions of the periodic table and bringing rich dividends. The coordination chemistry of a particular metal ion is to a large extent determined by its size, charge and valence configuration²⁻⁴. In the chemistry of main-group elements and to a large extent lanthanide and actinide elements, the dominant factors are the size and charge associated with the metal ion. For example, the very basis for the different biological roles of Na^I and K^I or Mg^{II} and Ca^{II} are due to these factors. For the transition elements, the effects arising from valence shell configuration are of paramount importance and often far outweigh the effects of charge and size. A specific *dⁿ* configuration will lead to preferences in coordination number and geometry as a result of ligand field stabilisation energies. Further, kinetic aspects of ligand substitution and electron-transfer reactions are greatly influenced by ligand field effects^{5,6}. For example, the rates of H₂O exchange of M(H₂O)₆ⁿ⁺ ions span a range from 10⁹ to 10⁻⁸ s⁻¹ at room temperature or the rates of electron transfer between Co(NH₃)₆²⁺ +

*Professor Priyadarajan Ray Memorial Lecture (1990) delivered at the 29th Annual Convention of Chemists, organised under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on 24 February 1993 at Rewa.

$\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$, $K = 10^{-8} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_2^{2+} + \text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{3+}$, $K = 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For a given d^n configuration, ligand field effects are dependent on both the ligands and the metal, and for a given group within the transition series, these effects become more pronounced on descending from the first to the second and to the third row. It is thus well known that while salts of nickel(II) may be tetrahedral, octahedral, or square-planar, those of platinum(II) are almost invariably square-planar and never tetrahedral. For the elements of the f -block (lanthanides and actinides), the large size coupled with their high charge enable them to form compounds with a relatively high coordination number of 8 or more, which is certainly higher than is usually encountered in transition metal coordination chemistry⁷.

The author's laboratory, during the past three decades, has been actively pursuing the coordination behaviour of several metal ions of the transition, lanthanide and actinide group elements with a relatively wide diversity of ligands. Out of all the metals investigated, it is proposed to highlight the contributions in the area of coordination chemistry of cobalt here. This interest arises as several ligands, e.g. the biologically important imidazole ligand, form a number of homoleptic tetrahedral or octahedral compounds with cobalt(II) but fail to do so with cobalt(III) and result only in the formation of heteroleptic octahedral complexes. This review will be directed mostly to the heteroleptic octahedral complexes of cobalt(III) containing oxime type of ligand and imidazole base and comparison wherever necessary, will be made with other complexes of the metal containing imidazole but no oxime type of ligand. The choice of the oxime or the oxime-based ligand will be clear from the discussion which follows. First, the oximes are ambidentate ligands⁸ capable of coordinating through either O- or N-donors. The various known modes of possible metal-oxime linking are shown in structures 1-4 (electrical charges not shown).

Oximes can react in a neutral manner or

in the form of conjugate base. They may be mono- or polydentate and can react with long-chain alkylamines giving multidentate oxime based Schiff bases containing several donor sites. They may form a complex with a metal as such or in presence of another base, e.g. pyridine, imidazole etc., to form mixed ligand (heteroleptic) complexes that are very similar to those employed in nature. Second, the oxime complexes of cobalt(III) (the cobaloximes) closely mimic the properties associated with vitamin B₁₂ and are used as model compounds⁹. The fact that vitamin B₁₂ is a cobalt complex containing a cobalt atom at the centre of the molecule and a stable Co-C bond clearly justify that an inorganic chemist can contribute to a number of interesting problems in biochemistry. Considerable amount of research has been focussed on the synthesis and investigation of model complexes and a number of these abiological systems exhibit properties shown by B₁₂ itself. The general structural features of the molecule are the central cobalt(III) ion bound by four nitrogen atoms from the pyrrole groups of the macrocyclic corrin ring that resembles a porphyrin ring at first glance, but is not fully conjugated and therefore, quite different chemically from porphyrin. The various derivatives of B₁₂ result most commonly from changes in the axial ligands bound to the cobalt and the common feature of the different models is that each possesses a very strong equatorial ligand field provided by the bis(dioximato) system or a single chelating tetradentate ligand. These and the related macrocyclic ligands have been invariably used as model compounds as they

reproduce the fundamental reactions of cobalamins and closely simulate the reactions of vitamin B₁₂⁹⁻¹⁴ that is so essential for all higher animals but seems to be synthesised exclusively by bacteria. Further, several compounds containing conjugated systems which act as bis-bidentate or tetradentate chelating ligands lying in the equatorial plane of square-pyramidal or square-bipyramidal structures were also proposed as models for the naturally occurring complexes of the corrin ring^{9,15}. Cobaloximes are reported to be useful reagents in synthetic organic chemistry and are employed as protecting groups in the synthesis of amino acids¹⁶. In view of the biological and synthetic significance of cobaloximes, the macrocyclic ring systems and the imidazole ligand, a range of non-homoleptic complexes of cobaloximes were synthesised and their stereochemical, electrochemical and biochemical characteristics were investigated. In what follows, we shall outline the details of a series of such complexes that are potential models for B₁₂.

Bis(vicinal dioxime) complexes

We have been able to synthesise¹⁷⁻²³ a number of cobaloximes by interaction with imidazole derivatives that have the general formula [Co(DH)₂(L)(X)] (DH = the monoanion of dimethylglyoxime; X = Cl, CNS, CNSe, N₃, ClO₄, BF₄, NO₂, NO₃; L = imidazole, benzimidazole and their derivatives). The report of Schrauzer²⁴ on the reactivity of BF₃.Et₂O with bis(dimethylglyoximato)nickel(II), [Ni(DH)₂] to form yellow planar macrocyclic complex bis(difluoroboron dimethylglyoximato)nickel(II), [Ni(DBF₂)₂] also prompted us to synthesise, and elucidate the stereochemistry and stability of six-coordinated cobalt(III) complexes [Co(DBF₂)₂(L)(X)]⁺ (X = Cl, CNS; L = Im or its derivative) containing 14-membered macrocyclic ligand system resembling the corrin sys-

tem²⁵, and prepared by the reaction of BF₃.Et₂O with the parent cobaloximes containing an imidazole base.

All these complexes are characterised by magnetic susceptibility, electrical conductivity, electronic, ir, nmr (¹H and ¹³C) and mass spectra as well as thermogravimetric measurements. The infrared spectra suggest the *trans*-structure for these complexes as substantiated by the nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectral evidences. The triatomic ambidentate pseudohalides, thiocyanate or selenocyanate, although expected to coordinate through the harder N-end to the typical hard cobalt(III)²⁶ are shown to be bonded through the S-end. The position of bands and particularly the intensity and sharpness of the ν_{CN} band for both the pseudohalo complexes clearly favour Co-S (or Se) bonding²⁷ (Fig. 1). This change in behaviour from hard to soft character of cobalt(III) is facilitated by ligands like dimethylglyoxime (DH₂) that are soft or

Fig. 1. Partial infrared spectra, ν_{CN} of (a) (—) [Co(DH)₂(SeCN)(1-Allm)] and (b) (---) [Co(DH)₂(SeCN)(1-Vi-2-MeIm)].

⁺(DH₂ represents neutral dimethylglyoxime and DH⁻ its monoanion; DBF₂ represents the monoanion of the boronic ester ligand difluoroboron dimethylglyoxime (1,8-diboro-1,1,6,3-tetrafluoro-2,7,9,14-tetraoxa-2,6,10,13-tetraaza-4,5,11,12-tetramethylcyclotetradeca-3,5,10,12-tetraene), and the archaic symbolisms CNS and CNSe indicate only the presence of pseudohalides without specifying their mode of bonding).

have π -acceptor capacity and imidazole, which is also a good π -acceptor in spite of its being a good σ -donor.

Both ^1H nmr²⁸ as well as ^{13}C nmr^{28,29} spectra are employed in the study of cobaloxime compounds to examine the *cis*- and *trans*-influences, axial ligand and conformational equilibria. The chemical shift of the organic group depends on several

factors, including electronic and steric effects of the axial and equatorial ligands. On the basis of nmr technique it was shown earlier^{30,31} that in certain cobalt(III) complexes containing bis-bidentate ligands, e.g. ethylenediamine or acetylacetonate ion, facile *cis-trans*-interconversion took place. However, the variable temperature nmr shifts of imidazole cobaloximes clearly reveal its rigid *trans*-structure. The axially coordinated anions in cobaloximes affected the nmr chemical shifts due to electronically induced (e.g. through bond) changes in the electronic environment around the carbon centre. Thus, on going from X = Cl to N₃ to NCS in [Co(DH)₂(Im)(X)] complexes, the ^{13}C chemical shifts of the CH₃ groups of dimethylglyoximate skeleton change progressively from 12.4 to 13.0 to 13.2 ppm and the imine carbon chemical shifts vary from 152.0 to 154.2

TABLE 1— ^{13}C CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF SOME [Co(DH)₂(X)(Im)] COMPLEXES^a

Compd.	DH ₂ carbons		Imidazole carbons			
	Oxime CH ₃	Imine C = N	C-2	C-4	C-5	R
Imidazole ^b			136.0	122.3	122.3	
Dimethylglyoxime ^b	9.23	154.12				
[Co(DH) ₂ (Cl)(1-EtIm)] ^b	12.42	151.97		127.6	121.8	15.89 34.86
[Co(DH) ₂ (Cl)(1-AllIm)] ^b	12.45	151.97	138.6	127.6	122.4	50.05 118.93 133.63
[Co(DH) ₂ (Cl)(2-iPrIm)] ^b	12.45	152.45	158.01	127.03	117.21	21.75 25.37
[Co(DH) ₂ (N ₃)(1-MeIm)] ^c	13.02	153.68	140.39	129.11	123.99	35.67
[Co(DH) ₂ (N ₃)(1-ViIm)] ^c	13.04	154.05	139.20	129.93	119.13	130.49 105.61
[Co(DH) ₂ (N ₃)(1,2-DiMeIm)] ^c	13.05	162.28	135.15	128.41	121.84	45.33 10.91
[Co(DH) ₂ (N ₃)(1-Vi,2-MeIm)] ^c	13.12	154.46	—	129.52	120.51	129.76 106.67 34.85
[Co(DH) ₂ (N ₃)(2-PrIm)] ^c	13.08	154.21	—	125.9	—	95.69 23.60
[Co(DH) ₂ (SCN)(1-EtIm)] ^c	13.01	154.59	138.97 138.73	128.73 128.49	122.23 122.06	44.84 15.88
[Co(DH) ₂ (SCN)(1-AllIm)] ^c	13.13 13.01	155.99 154.65	139.55 139.32	128.85 128.61	122.88 122.70	133.53 120.81 51.92
[Co(DH) ₂ (SCN)(2-MeIm)] ^c	13.36	155.00 154.82	—	129.26	116.97	13.07
[Co(DH) ₂ (SCN)(2-iPrIm)] ^c	13.42 13.13	155.17 155.00	— —	128.15 —	117.56 —	26.30 22.08
[Co(DH) ₂ (SCN)(1,2-DiMeIm)] ^c	13.18	155.32 154.14	— —	127.74 —	— —	34.53 14.00

^aAll values in ppm relative to internal CD₃NO₂ or DMF-d₇ at ambient temperatures downfield to TMS. ^bIn DMF. ^cIn CD₃NO₂

to 155.1 ppm. The ¹³C nmr chemical shifts are presented in Table 1.

The cyclic voltammetric measurements of cobaloxime complexes in MeCN invariably show waves corresponding to successive reductions of cobalt(III) → cobalt(II) → cobalt(I)¹¹. In some cases, the presence of a reversible oxidative peak at +1.0 to +1.3 V is observed²² corresponding to one-electron oxidation to cobalt(IV). A similar observation has been reported and formation of cobalt(IV) has been confirmed by spectral titrations and cyclic voltammetry^{32,33}. All these clearly suggest the existence of cobalt in the +3 state, in contrast to the alkylcobaloximes where the metal seems to be in a formal +2 state¹¹. The cyclic voltammetric peak potentials for the macrocyclic boronic ester complexes are presented in Table 2, and the cyclic voltammogram of one of the complexes, [Co(DBF₂)₂(SCN)(Im)] (+ve side of SCE), is shown in Fig. 2.

Symmetric tetradentate dioxime Schiff base complexes

Cobalt(III) complexes containing a wide variety of equatorial ligands containing N₄-systems are known³⁴⁻³⁸ to have a possible biochemical relevance to vitamin B₁₂ coenzyme. To gain more insight into the interaction of dioxime Schiff base complexes of cobalt, several tetradentate dioxime

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of [Co(DBF₂)₂(SCN)(Im)] (+ve side of SCE).

Schiff base ligands containing N₄ donor sets have been synthesised and their ligating behaviour studied. These tetradentate dioxime Schiff base complexes are H₂Me₂en (7), H₂Me(Ph)en (8), H₂Me₂pn (9) and H₂Me₂*o*-phen (10), synthesised by the reaction of isonitrosoethylmethylketone or isonitrosopropiophenone³⁹ with ethylenediamine, propylenediamine or 1,2-diaminobenzene. These tetradentate ligands react with cobalt(II) salts to yield cobalt(III) complexes of general formula [Co(HL)X₂]⁴⁰, where H₂L = H₂Me₂en, H₂Me(ph)en,

TABLE 2—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC PEAK POTENTIAL (V vs SCE) DATA^a OF MACROCYCLIC BORONIC ESTER COMPLEXES IN MeCN AT 25° (PLATINUM WORKING ELECTRODE)

Compd.	+ve side of SCE (oxdn.)			-ve side of SCE (redn.)		
	<i>E</i> _{pa}	<i>E</i> _{pc}	<i>E</i> ₂₉₈	<i>E</i> _{pc}	<i>E</i> _{pa}	<i>E</i> ₂₉₈
[Co(DBF ₂) ₂ (SCN)(Im)]	1.32	1.23	1.275	-0.62 -0.92 -1.20	-0.53 -0.80 -1.09	-0.58 -0.86 -1.15
[Co(DBF ₂) ₂ (SCN)(1-MeIm)]	1.30	1.20	1.25	-0.59 -0.92 -1.20	-0.46 -0.74 -1.08	-0.53 -0.84 -1.14
[Co(DBF ₂) ₂ (SCN)(2-MeIm)]	1.20	1.07	1.135	-0.56 -0.86 -1.18 -1.97	-0.30 -0.73 -1.02 -1.86	-0.43 -0.81 -1.10 -1.92
[Co(DBF ₂) ₂ (SCN)(4-MeIm)]	1.02	0.94	0.98	- -0.84 -1.19 -1.82	- -0.74 -1.12 -1.26	- -0.79 -1.15 -1.54

^aConditions are as follows: scan rate, 50 mV s⁻¹; solute concentration, 3.0 × 10⁻³ M; supporting electrolyte, TEAP; the reported *E*_{pc} values are uncorrected for junction potentials.

H_2Me_2pn , H_2Me_2o -phen; X = Cl, Br, I, CNS, CNSe (11–14). These ligands behave as monodeprotonated uninegative ligands coordinating through the four nitrogen donors with simultaneous formation of intramolecular hydrogen bridges. These complexes containing hydrogen bridges are expected to form bridged macrocyclic complexes^{41–45} on reaction with Lewis acids, e.g. BX_3 (X = F, OH, OCH_3 , OC_2H_5 , o - iC_3H_7 , o - nC_4H_9), AlX_3 (X = Cl, o - iC_3H_7), $SiCl_4$ and $SnCl_4$. This is realised in the formation of difluoroboron bridged macrocyclic complexes by interaction of $[Co(HMe_2en)X_2]$ with $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ in dry diethyl ether medium. All the complexes are six-coordinated, diamagnetic

and non-electrolytic octahedral in nature and the non-electrolytic behaviour remains unaltered even after 24–28 h indicating that axial anions are rather tightly bound to the cobalt(III) centre.

The ESCA measurements indicate an increase in total charge on the four nitrogen atoms of the ligands on coordination to cobalt(III)⁴⁶. In the specific case of $[Co(HMe_2en)Cl_2]$, the increase in total charge on the N atoms upon coordination is $2 \times (0.11) + 2 \times (0.10) = +0.42$ charge units. Charge on each chloride ion simultaneously increases from -1.00 to -0.66 , i.e. an increase of $+0.34$. Summing up all these increments on the ligating atoms one gets $0.42 + 2 \times (0.34) = 1.10$. The value is comparable with the change in the charge of cobalt on coordination, -0.99 charge units. In case of the corresponding bromo complex, the agreement between increase and decrease of charge is very good, although for the iodo complex, the agreement seems to be less perfect. A comparison of the chloro, bromo and iodo complexes shows that the charges of the nitrogen ligating atoms remain almost constant and that the charge on the cobalt centre decreases steadily from Cl^- to I^- , in agreement with the electron donating properties of the halides. The binding energies for the H_2Me_2en ligand and its cobalt(III) complexes are given in Table 3 and the ESCA spectra for the H_2Me_2en ligand is shown Fig. 3.

TABLE 3—BINDING ENERGIES (eV) FOR THE LIGAND H_2Me_2en AND SOME OF ITS COBALT(III) COMPLEXES

Comp.	E_b (eV)		$Co^2p_{3/2}$	X (Cl, Br, I)
	$N1s$	$N1s^{*}$		
H_2Me_2en	400.6	399.0		
$[Co(HMe_2en)Cl_2]$	401.4	399.7	781.2	$198.4^2p_{3/2}$
$[Co(HMe_2en)Br_2]$	401.5	399.8	781.1	$182.0^3p_{3/2}$
$[Co(HMe_2en)I_2]$	401.5	399.7	780.7	$619.9^3d_{5/2}$

Imidazole adducts of the tetradentate dioxime Schiff base complexes

Realising the importance of dioxime based Schiff bases, the imidazole and derivatives, the synthesis of a number of complexes of imidazole with cobalt(III) containing tetradentate dioxime Schiff

Fig. 3 Carbon 1s XPS spectrum of the free ligand H-Me₂en (upper curve) showing a broad peak, composed of several signals, representing both the low energy methyl carbons and the high energy skeleton carbons of the ligand. For comparison, the lower curve shows the C 1s spectrum of Ph₄PClO₄.

bases have been achieved¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The complexes obtained are of the type: [Co(Me₂en)(Im)₂] λ (X = Cl, Br, I, SCN, SeCN), [Co(HMe₂en)(Im)₂] λ (X = Cl, Br, ClO₄), [Co(HMe₂pn)(Im)₂](ClO₄)₂, [Co(Me₂o-phen)(Im) λ] (X = Cl, Br, I, CNS, CNSe) and [Co(Me₂o-phen)(Im)₂] λ (X = Cl, Br, I, SCN, SeCN), where the ligands act as mono- or dianions with or without the hydrogen bridge.

The electronic spectra of [Co(HL) λ] and their imidazole adducts discussed above measured in DMF or DMSO and in the solid state (diffuse reflectance spectrum) were identical confirming the rigid nature of the complexes. These bands have been assigned⁵⁰. In the infrared spectra it is seen that the $\nu_{C=N}$ (azomethine) mode of the ligands shifts to lower frequencies in the complexes and the ν_{N-O} observed in the complexes at 1130-1180 cm⁻¹ favour the N-coordination of the oximes⁵¹. The band of low intensity at 2360 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{OH}

mode of intramolecularly H-bonded NOH group in the complexes⁵², and a new band at 520 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{Co-N} ⁵³. A strong band at 756-780 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the $\delta_{C=N-O}$ mode while bands at 990, 921 and 910 cm⁻¹ are due to the deformation modes of the ligand⁵⁴. In [Co(BF₂Me₂en) λ] λ (X = Cl, Br) complexes, the ν_{B-F} appears at 1005-1030 cm⁻¹ and the ν_{B-O} at²⁴ 830-850 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4). In the thiocyanato and selenocyanato complexes, the $\nu_{C=N}$ bands appear as a strong and intense band at 2100-2115 cm⁻¹ indicating bonding through^{55,56} the S or Se end. The ν_{C-S} mode observed at 705 cm⁻¹ is indicative of S-coordination. This observation is in agreement with our earlier¹⁷ and other observations⁵⁷.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of the tetradentate H₂Me₂en in DMSO gives two sharp singlets at δ 1.88 and 2.04 due to the two types of magnetically non-equivalent CH₃ protons, which shift downfield in the complexes to δ 2.45-2.50 and 2.5-2.65 respectively. The signal at δ 3.75 in the ligand assigned to the -CH₂-CH₂- protons shifts to δ 4.8 in the complexes. In the ¹³C nmr spectra of H₂Me₂en the two non-equivalent CH₃ groups give signals at 8.64 and 12.96 ppm shifting downfield in the complexes to 12.98-15.36 and 17.89-20.16 ppm respectively.

Fig. 4. Partial IR spectra of [Co(Me₂enBF₂)Br]

TABLE 4— ^{13}C NMR SHIFTS OF THE IMIDAZOLES, $\text{H}_2\text{Me}_2\text{en}$ AND THE COBALT(III) COMPLEXES^a

Compd.	Ligand carbons					Imidazole carbons			
	CH_3^a	CH_3^b	$\text{C}^c\text{-C}^c$	$\text{C}^d\text{-C}^d$	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$	c2	C4	C5	R
$\text{H}_2\text{Me}_2\text{en}$	8.64	12.96	156.48	165.12	52.32	—	—	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})\text{Cl}_2]$	15.36	20.16	160.32	176.64	56.64	—	—	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})\text{Br}_2]$	12.98	17.89	157.97	174.34	54.54	—	—	—	—
Im						136.24	122.50	122.50	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{Im})_2]\text{Cl}$	12.48	17.28	159.23	178.24	52.42	134.73	123.4	117.52	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{Im})_2]\text{Br}$	12.42	16.82	150.42	175.99	51.91	136.22	126.12	117.76	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{Im})(\text{SCN})]$	11.76	16.56	167.05	177.83	49.92	134.71	124.15	118.27	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(1\text{-ViIm})_2]\text{Cl}$	12.68	17.11	150.78	176.76	52.03	137.26	128.08	116.96	103.93
									129.38 1-Vi
$[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})(1\text{-MeIm})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	12.48	17.28	157.44	178.56	51.84	138.24	125.76	122.88	33.6 1-Me
$[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})(1\text{-ViIm})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	13.44	18.24	157.4	178.2	51.84	127.68	125.76	118.08	105.6
									119.04 N-Vi

^aAll values in ppm relative to internal $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$ resonating at 39.6 ppm as a heptet.

The ethylene carbons resonate at 52.31 and 54.31–56.64 ppm in the ligand and the complexes respectively. The two other carbons in the biacetylmonoxime skeleton resonate at 156.48 and 165.12 ppm in the complexes (Table 4). Similar shift in the ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra are also observed for $\text{H}_2\text{Me}(\text{Ph})\text{en}$ ligand and the complexes.

The non-alkyl cobalt(III) complexes, $[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})\text{-X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{SCN}, \text{SeCN}$) involving the tetradentate dioxime Schiff base $\text{H}_2\text{Me}_2\text{en}$ react with imidazole and its derivatives to form complexes

of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{B})_2]\text{X}$ ($\text{B} = \text{imidazole}$ or 1-vinylimidazole; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) or $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})\text{-}(\text{B})(\text{X})]$ ($\text{X} = \text{SCN}, \text{SeCN}$). The intramolecular hydrogen bridge in the $[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2\text{en})\text{X}_2]$ complexes is absent in the imidazole derivatives and the tetradentate N_4 donor ligand acts as a dianionic ligand in $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{B})_2]\text{X}$ (**15**) and $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})\text{-}(\text{B})(\text{X})]$ (**16**) complexes. Further, the difluoroboron bridged macrocyclic complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{BF}_2\text{Me}_2\text{en})\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{S} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) reacted with stoichiometric amounts of imidazole in ether-methanol medium to yield $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(\text{B})_2]\text{X}$ complexes.

Fig. 5. ^1H nmr spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(1\text{-ViIm})_2]\text{Cl}$ in DMSO-d_6 .

B = Im, 1-Vi-Im

X = SCN, SeCN

X = Cl, Br, I

(17)

(18)

R = H; Im
R = Me; 1-MeIm
R = Et; 1-Et Im
R = Vi; 1-Vi Im

R = H; Im

R = Me; 1-Me Im

R = Et; 1-Et Im

R = Vi; 1-Vi Im

R = Al; 1-Al Im

All these complexes (15–18) were appropriately characterised as their parent hydrogen bridged complexes (5) by electrical conductance, electronic, infrared and nmr (¹H and ¹³C) spectral data. The electronic, infrared and nmr spectra are very similar and new bands and signals for the imidazole ligand appear. That the hydrogen bonding is absent in the imidazole derivatives is substantiated by the fact that the low intensity

band at 2360 cm⁻¹ in the infrared due to the intramolecular H-bonding⁵⁸ in the parent [Co-(HMe₂en)X₂] complexes⁴⁰ is absent in [Co(Me₂en)-(B)₂]X or [Co(Me₂en)(B)X] complexes. Further, the NOH proton resonating at δ 8.28 in the ligand disappears on complexation. The equivalence of H-4 and H-5 of free imidazole at δ 7.15 is lost on coordination and separate signals are observed^{59,60}. The 1-vinylimidazole complexes show

Fig. 6 ^{13}C nmr spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(1\text{-ViIm})_2]\text{Cl}$ in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$.

a sequence of proton patterns in which the chemical shifts between the X and the AB protons (ABX spin system) vary significantly. The position and large splittings of the single proton signal at around δ 7.20 suggest that this is due to the H_X part while the olefinic protons resonate at around δ 5.5 (for H_A) and 4.98 (for H_B) and the small splittings observed within this band are quite consistent with the expected geminal coupling⁶¹. The magnitude of the various couplings are $J(\text{H}_A\text{H}_B) = 5.7$ Hz, $J(\text{H}_B\text{H}_X) = 8.5$ Hz and $J(\text{H}_A\text{H}_X) = 15.7$ Hz. The ^{13}C nmr spectra of these complexes (Table 4) exhibit a clear downfield shift of the non-equivalent carbons of two CH_3 groups from 8.64 and 12.96 ppm to 11.7–15.3 and 16.5–20.1 ppm regions respectively, and the two carbons C^c and C^d of the dioxime skeleton shift from 156.48 and 165.12 ppm to 150–167 and 176–178 ppm respectively. While the shift for C^c is negligible, the C^d experiences a substantial downfield shift on complexation^{40,58}. The methylene $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$ carbons appear in the region of 50–60 ppm. The ^{13}C resonance lines of imidazole experience a downfield shift on complexation. The C-2, C-4 and C-5 of the imidazole rings in the complexes resonate at 134.7–137.2, 123.4–128.0 and 117.0–118.27 ppm respectively. The N-vinyl carbons resonate at 103.93 and 129.38 ppm. The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2\text{en})(1\text{-ViIm})_2]\text{Cl}$ are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 respectively.

14, 19, 20

Conjugated symmetric tetradentate Schiff base complexes

The conjugated tetradentate ligand systems are chelating agents coordinating to four equatorial positions of square-pyramidal or octahedral structures of metal centres and are known to form compounds which serve as models for the natural corrin ring^{9,34,62}, and thus for vitamin B_{12} and its coenzyme. The neutral conjugated tetradentate ligand, $\text{H}_2\text{Me}_2o\text{-phen}$ (10) obtained by the reaction of biacetylmonoxime with 1,2-diaminobenzene forms complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2o\text{-phen})\text{X}_2]$ (14) which in turn reacts with imidazole to form $[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2o\text{-phen})(\text{Im})(\text{X})]$ (19). However, the direct interaction of CoX_2 , $\text{H}_2\text{Me}_2o\text{-phen}$ and imidazole results in the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2o\text{-phen})(\text{Im})_2]\text{X}$ (20) ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{SCN}, \text{SeCN}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$). These are diamagnetic complexes and are characterised by electronic, infrared and nmr (^1H and ^{13}C) spectra. The hydrogen bridge in $[\text{Co}(\text{HMe}_2o\text{-phen})(\text{X})_2]$ (14) is ruptured on reaction with imidazole forming the complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{Me}_2o\text{-phen})(\text{Im})(\text{X})]$ (19) where the ligand acts as a dianionic ligand⁴⁸. The electronic and infrared spectral bands are adequately assigned to support the structure. In these complexes, the pseudohalides are bonded through the S- or Seend⁶³, as observed earlier, and the nitrate⁶⁴

or perchlorate⁶⁵ anions are not involved in bonding to the cobalt(III) centre. The ¹H nmr spectrum of H₂Me₂*o*-phen ligand exhibits two sharp signals of equal intensity at δ 1.9 and 2.7 due to two magnetically non-equivalent methyl protons and the aromatic protons as a complex multiplet centred at δ 7.8. In the complexes, however, only one intense 12-proton singlet at δ 2.4–2.45 (for 4CH₃ groups) is observed and the signal for aromatic protons is either virtually absent or is not well-resolved. This phenomenon was also observed earlier⁶⁶. The H-2, H-4 and H-5 protons of the coordinated imidazole resonate⁶⁷ at δ 7.5, 7.3 and 6.7 respectively. In the ¹³C nmr spectrum, the ligand H₂Me₂*o*-phen displays two sharp signals at δ 8.34 and 12.6 due to the two non-equivalent CH₃ groups. The aromatic carbons resonate at 127, 128 and 139 ppm and the C^c and C^d carbons resonate at 152.4 and 153.3 ppm respectively. In all the complexes, as in the case of ¹H nmr signals of the CH₃ groups, all the four methyl carbons resonate to give a strong singlet at 16.2–16.6 ppm. The C^c and C^d carbons give a single signal in the region of 153–158 ppm. The aromatic carbon signals seem to merge with the imidazole carbon signals or are not observed as in the case of the proton signals. The C-2, C-4 and C-5 of the imidazole ring appear at 140, 129, 123 ppm and in addition, in the 2-methylimidazole complex, the ¹³C of 2-MeIm resonates at 16.37 ppm.

The electrochemical measurement of the complexes in acetonitrile is characterised by three distinct reduction waves at -0.69, -1.0 to -1.2 and -1.92 to -1.94 V corresponding to reduction processes Co^{III} → Co^{II}, Co^{II} → Co^I and Co^I → Co⁰ respectively. These values are very similar to the values reported in literature^{11,68}.

The thermal decomposition study of all the complexes in the temperature range 40–800°, reveals that the decomposition starts at 200–230° and on further heating ultimately at around 600° Co₃O₄ is formed as the stable end-product. The mass spectra of the free ligands and their cobalt(III) complexes have been obtained. For the complexes, the molecular ion peak is not obtained and

only the peaks due to the ligand and its fragmentation products are observed, the most abundant species being CH₃-C=N⁺-H (*m/z* 42) followed by CH₃-C≡N (*m/z* 41).

Conclusion :

These studies reveal that the oximes or oxime based Schiff base ligands form complexes with cobalt(III) in presence of imidazole bases. These are non-alkyl analogues of compounds known to function as models for vitamin B₁₂. In conclusion, it may be pointed out that in the search for true model compounds for vitamin B₁₂, the inorganic chemist has probably benefitted more from B₁₂ than B₁₂ has from him. This is due to the fact that a great deal of new and interesting inorganic chemistry has been uncovered while studying systems related to B₁₂, although a limited amount of insight into the properties of this vitamin has been obtained.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to C.S.I.R. and U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support, and acknowledges the generous laboratory facilities in collecting various data provided by Prof. A. Chakravorty (Jadavpur), Professors H. Schmidbaur and A. Schmidpeter (Munich, Germany), Dr. Y. Inoguchi (Gakushuin, Japan) and Prof. S. Ahrlund (Lund, Sweden). It is a pleasure to acknowledge the contributions of all my research coworkers for their help in completion of the experiments and for providing a stimulating atmosphere in the Department.

References

- 1 A WERNER, *Z Anorg Chem.*, 1893, **3**, 267
- 2 F A COTTON and G WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 5th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1988
- 3 N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNSHAW, "Chemistry of the Elements", Pergamon, Oxford, 1984
- 4 D F SIRIVIER, P W ATKINS and C H LANGFORD, "Inorganic Chemistry", W H Freeman & Co. New York, 1990
- 5 F BASOLO and R G PEARSON, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions, A Study of Metal Complexes in Solution", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1968
- 6 H TAUBE, "Electron Transfer Reactions of Complex Ions in Solution", Academic Press, New York, 1970
- 7 A F WEILS "Structural Inorganic Chemistry", 4th ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1975

8. A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **13**, 1.
9. G. N. SCHRAUZER, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1968, **1**, 97.
10. G. N. SCHRAUZER and G. KLATEL, *Angew. Chem.*, 1956, **77**, 180.
11. G. N. SCHRAUZER and R. J. WINDGASSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 3738.
12. J. M. PRATT and P. J. CRAIG, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 331.
13. D. G. BROWN, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **18**, 177.
14. P. J. TOSCANO and L. G. MARZILLI, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **31**, 105.
15. A. BIGOTO, G. COSTA, G. MESTRONI, G. PELLIZER, A. PUXEDDU, E. REISENHOFER, L. STEFANI and G. TAUZHER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1970, **4**, 41.
16. H. ECKERT, G. N. SCHRAUZER and I. UGI, *Tetrahedron*, 1975, **31**, 1399.
17. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1109.
18. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1985, **15**, 839.
19. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 387.
20. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 422.
21. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1986, **56**, 14.
22. J. K. DAS, V. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. DASH, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1986, **11**, 170.
23. J. K. DAS, V. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. DASH, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, **97**, 303.
24. G. N. SCHRAUZER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1962, **95**, 1438.
25. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 1857.
26. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3533.
27. J. L. ALLISON and J. L. BURMEISTER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **16**, 185.
28. H. P. C. HOGGENKAMP in "Cobalamin: Biochemistry and Pathophysiology", ed. B. M. BABIOR, Wiley, New York, 1975, p. 1.
29. C. BIED-CHARRETON, B. SEPTE and A. GAUDMER, *Org. Mag. Res.*, 1975, **7**, 116.
30. G. ROYCHAUDHURY and K. C. DASH, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1980, **68**, 319.
31. J. K. DAS and K. C. DASH, *Z. Naturforsch. Teil B*, 1985, **40**, 470.
32. J. HALPERN, M. S. CHAN, J. HANSON, T. S. ROCHE and J. TOPICH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 1606.
33. J. TOPICH and J. HALPERN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 1339.
34. B. T. GOLDING, *Chem. Br.*, 1990, 950.
35. G. COSTA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **8**, 63.
36. D. DODD and M. D. JOHNSON, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, **52**, 1.
37. M. K. WITMAN and J. H. WEBER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1977, **23**, 363.
38. R. D. W. KEMMIT and D. R. RUSSEL in "Comprehensive Organometallic Chemistry", ed. G. WILKINSON, Pergamon, Oxford, 1982, Vol. 5, p. 80.
39. W. H. HARTUNG and F. CROSSBY, *Org. Synth.*, 1943, **2**, 363.
40. M. MOHAPATRA and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 342.
41. S. C. JACKLES and N. J. ROSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 1232.
42. W. FEDDER, F. UMLAND and E. HOHAUS, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1980, **471**, 77.
43. F. S. STEPHENS, R. S. VAGG and E. C. WALTON, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1981, **47**, 197.
44. Y. NONAKA and K. HAMADA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 3185.
45. F. S. STEPHENS and R. S. VAGG, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **89**, 203.
46. K. C. DASH, B. FOLKESSON, R. LARSSON and M. MOHAPATRA, *J. Electron Spectrosc. Related Phenomena*, 1989, **49**, 343.
47. M. MOHAPATRA and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 482.
48. M. MOHAPATRA and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 788.
49. M. MOHAPATRA, V. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. DASH, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1991, **21**, 275.
50. Y. YAMANO, I. MASUDA and K. SHIMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 1581.
51. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 179.
52. K. BURGER, "Coordination Chemistry: Experimental Methods", Butterworths, London, 1973.
53. N. YAMAZAKI and Y. HOHOKABE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 63.
54. L. J. BOUCHER and J. J. KATZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1340.
55. A. H. NORBURY, P. E. SHAW and A. I. P. SINHA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 742.
56. J. ALLISON and J. L. BURMEISTER, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **16**, 185.
57. L. G. MARZILLI, J. G. SALERNO and L. A. EPPS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2050.
58. M. MOHAPATRA, V. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. DASH, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 1509.
59. T. J. BATTERHAM, "NMR Spectra of Simple Heterocycles", Wiley, New York, 1973.
60. R. H. CARLSON and T. L. BROWN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 268.
61. J. ELGUERO, C. MARZIN and J. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 357.
62. T. -T. TSOO, M. LOOTS and J. HALPERN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 623.
63. D. C. CALABRO, B. A. HARRISON, G. T. PALMER, M. K. MOGUEL, R. L. ROBBERT and J. L. BURMEISTER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 4311.
64. C. C. ADDISON and D. SUTTON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 195.
65. J. W. L. MARTIN, J. H. TIMMONS, A. E. MARTELL, P. RUDOLF and A. CLEARFIELD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 814.
66. V. V. RAMANUJAN and V. ALEXANDER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 3129.
67. K. C. DASH and G. ROYCHAUDHURY, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1981, **72**, 269.
68. N. MAKI, Y. ISHIUCHI and S. SAKURABA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, **42**, 3156, 3166.